

ANALYSIS OF ANEMIA PREGNANT WOMEN ON STUNTING INCIDENT RATES INCIBEER HEALTH CENTER

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Abstract: The incidence of stunting in the world, in Indonesia, in several provinces, especially in the 12 stunting priority provinces, as well as in several districts throughout Indonesia, is still high. The occurrence of stunting has short-term and long-term impacts. The short-term impact of disrupted brain development, intelligence, impaired physical growth, and metabolic disorders in the body, for the emergence and long-term impact is decreased cognitive ability and learning achievement, decreased immunity so that people get sick easily, and a high risk of diabetes, obesity, heart and blood vessel disease, cancer, stroke, and disability in old age. The accumulation of these two impacts can reduce the quality of resources, productivity and the nation's competitiveness. The incidence of stunting in Indonesia can be caused by many factors. These factors contribute both directly and indirectly. One factor that is related is anemia in pregnant women. Where anemia in pregnant women can cause stunted growth and development of the baby in the mother's womb. Stunting is a chronic nutritional disorder in children characterized by children being shorter than children in general. The aim of this research is to analyze pregnant women with anemia on the incidence of stunting in the Cibeber Community Health Center working area. This research method uses a quantitative approach, where the cross-sectional method is used. In this method, data is only taken once. This type of data uses secondary data. The results of this research obtained secondary data, that there is a direct or indirect relationship between anemia in pregnant women and the incidence of stunting. even though the data is not perpendicular. between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Between data on pregnant women with anemia, and the nutritional status of thin children and short children. The conclusion is that there isa relationship between pregnant women with anemia and the incidence of stunting at the Cibeber Community Health Center.

Keywords: Pregnant Women; Anemia; Stunting.

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Introduction

Stunting is the low ratio of height to age based on the table Z-Score at values ≤ -2 SD (UNICEF, 2015). *Stunting* be a marker of chronic nutritional deficiencies experienced over a long period of time (Vonaesch et al., 2017). *Stunting* can influence the development of cognitive and non-cognitive abilities that will be felt from pre-school to adolescence (Himaz, 2018). Prevalence *stunting* in the world has decreased from 32.7% to 22.9% since 2000-2016.

Likewise prevalence *stunting* in Southeast Asia which experienced a decline from 51.3% to 35.8% in 2000-2016 (UNICEF, WHO, & World Bank Group, 2017). The incidence of stunting in some poor and developing countries is still relatively very high. in Asia 55% and 39% in Africa Decrease in the number of incidents *stunting* This is inversely proportional to

the conditions *stunting* in Indonesia. The prevalence of short toddlers *orstuntingas* measured by height per age (TB/U) has increased by 1.2% since 2007-2013.

Vice President Asks Families to Prioritize Nutritional Needs. PAUDPEDIA—2020 UN statistics record that more than 149 million (22%) toddlers worldwide experience stunting, of which 6.3 million are young children or stunted toddlers are Indonesian toddlers. The prevalence of stunting in Indonesia is still high, namely 29.6%. (WAHYUNI, 2024)

There are many factors that cause stunting in Indonesia, which are very diverse and complex. Among these factors are the child while in the mother's womb. When pregnant, mothers experience anemia, which is caused by iron deficiency. Anemia in pregnant women is the amount of hemoglobin in the blood of less than 11 gram%. Anemia in pregnant women

causes pregnant women to look pale, tired quickly, tired and look lethargic. Anemia in pregnant women. Iron deficiency in pregnant women causes the growth and development of the fetus in the womb to be hampered. So the birth weight is less than normal weight. Long- term impacts can cause stunting in toddlers. Apart from several other factors.

Stunting is a toddler's height that is less than that of toddlers of the same age.

Low birth weight is a baby born from a mother's womb of less than 2500 grams. The baby's lack of weight has an impact on the baby's growth and development, including the baby's lack of sucking reflex. Babies are weaker than babies born normally. According to research by Dian Anisia (2010), the results showed that the proportion of history of pregnancy anemia in the case group was 18 (66.7%) A and those who did not suffer from anemia was 9 (33%), while the proportion of history of pregnancy anemia in the control group A was 17 (30.9%)A and those who did not suffer from anemia were 38 (69.1%). Analysis *Statistical test using the chi square test (value= 0.005 < 0.05) and OR 4.471* which shows there is a significant relationship between a history of pregnancy anemia and the incidence *stunting* in toddlers in Ketandan Dagangan Madiun Village. The results of the study showed that the proportion of history of pregnancy anemia in the case group was 18 (66.7%) A and those who did not suffer from anemia was 9 (33%), while the proportion of history of pregnancy anemia in the control group A was 17 (30.9%) A and those who did not suffer from anemia were 38 (69.1%). Analysis *Statistical test using the chi square test (Ivalue= 0.005 < 0.05) and OR 4.471* which shows there is a significant relationship between history of pregnancy anemia and the incidence *stunting* in toddlers in Ketandan Dagangan Madiun Village. Research Objective: Analyzing

anemic pregnant women on the incidence of stunting at the Cibeber Community Health Center.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Research methods

This research method uses a quantitative approach, with a cross sectional design. According to (Ariani, 2014) Cross sectional: "is a research to study the correlation between risk factors by approaching or collecting data at onetime only. Meanwhile, what is meant by quantitative data according to Creswell (2013) is: "Creswell 2012 says that quantitative research is research that works with numbers, where the data is in the form of numbers (scores or values, rankings or frequencies)

2. Type of research data using secondary data, namely data taken from the PWS KIA (SDIDTK) program report at the Cibeber Community Health Center, Cianjur Regency. Place and time of research

3. The research location is Cibeber Community Health Center, Cianjur Regency, while the research time is in April 2024.

4. Collection technique

The data collection technique uses documentation studies, namely collecting program data for the last 3 years, namely from 2020 data to 2022 data.

5. Data processing and data analysis techniques

Data processing and analysis techniques by means of data recapitulation using Excel. This data is data from the last 3 years, namely 2020, 2021 and 2022. The data was processed by data analysis using SPSS version 22. Then interpretation was carried out.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 1

Recapitulation of Pregnant Women Anemia at Cibeber Community Health Center 2020-2022

No	Village Name	Anemia in the mother pregnant			ket
		2020	2021	2022	
1	PT Condong	0	10	14	
2	Mayak	0	17	7	
3	Cisalak	0	1	4	
4	Cipetir	0	4	10	
5	Cikondang	0	7	4	
6	Kanoman	0	7	5	
7	Cibokor	0	2	13	
8	Cihaur	0	2	3	
9	Salagedang	0	5	2	
10	Cibadak	0	2	1	
11	Sukamanah	0	1	1	
	Amount	0	57	64	

Based on the recapitulation results of anemic pregnant women at the CibeberHealth Center in 2020-2022, it was found that the first highest anemia in 2021 was in Mayak Village, while the second highest was in Pt Condong Village with 14 people in 2021. Meanwhile, the third highest was in Cibokor Village in 2022.

Based on table 1, it can be seen that the highest number of pregnant women with anemia occurred in 2022, as many as 64, while the second highest number of pregnant women with anemia occurred in 2021, namely 57.

Meanwhile in 2020 there were no pregnant women with anemia. . Is it not reported or does it exist at all? If it was not reported, it can be assumed that it was not detected by officers.

This could mean that the longer it takes, the higher the number of pregnant women with anemia. However, it could also be interpreted that health workers, including midwives, are able to detect pregnant women with anemia. Anemic pregnancy can be detected through hemoglobin examination in pregnant women. So that the results of this examination can confirm the analysis of midwifery care for pregnant women.

TABLE 2

RECAPITULATION OF EARLY DETECTION OF CHILDREN'S GROWTH IN CIBEKER HEALTH CENTER YEAR 2020-2022

No	Village Name	Nutritional Status for 2020-2022						TOQ
		2020		2021		2022		
		Kurus	Short k	Kurus	Short k	Kurus	Short k	
1	Pt Leaning	3	2	2	-	-	-	
2	Mayak	2	1	2	-	-	-	
3	Cisalak	2	1	1	-	8	5	
4	Cipetir	3	1	33	-	-	-	
5	Cikondang	56	16	32	9	10	1	
6	Kanoman	4	1	2	-	1	-	
7	Cibokor	38	2	7	-	2	14	
8	Cihaur	20	1	38	-	-	-	
9	Salagedang	5	2	1	-	2	2	
10	Cibadak	5	1	2	-	-	-	
11	Sukamanah	4	1	2	-	3	2	
	Amount	142	29	122	9	26	24	

TABLE 3
STATISTICS

	Pregnant women Anemia 2020	Pregnant women Anemia a 2021	Pregnant women Anemia 2022	Thin 2020	Short 2020	Thin2021	Short k 2021	Kurus 2022	Short k 2022
Valid	12	12	12	12	12	12	7	7	6
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	5	6
Mean	.0000	9,583	10.6667	23.6667	4.8333	20.3333	7.43	7.43	8.00
Std. Error of Mean	.00000	4,513	5.01261	11.8483	2.51611	10.1319	3,351	3.35	3,751
Median	.0000	38	4,5000	4,5000	1,0000	2,0000	3.00	3.00	3.50
Mode	.00	4,500	1.00a	2.00a	1.00	2.00	2	2	2
Std. Deviation	.00000	15.63	17.3641	41.0439	8.71606	35.0981	8,867	8.86	9,187
Variance	.0000	480	9	5	3	78.6178	7	0.9	0
Range	.0000	244.4	301,515	1684.60	75,970	1231.87	9	684.4	0
Minimum	.00	47	63.00	6	28.00	25	19	23	23
Maximum	.00	56.00	1.00	140.00	1.00	121.00	1	25	1
Sum	.00	1.00	64.00	2.00	29.00	1.00	26	1	24
	.00	57.00	128.00	142.00	58.00	122.00	52	26	48
		115.0		284.00		244.00		52	

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

From the results of the Local Area Monitoring Report on Maternal and Child Health (PWS KIA) Early Growth and Development Intervention Detection Stimulation (SDIDTK) based on children's nutritional status in 2020-2022, it was found that the highest number of thin and stunted children was in 2020 in Cikondang Village, namely as many as thin children. 56 and 16 stunted children. Data on the nutritional status of the two thin children is in Cibokor Village in 2020 and Cihaur Village in 2021 with the same value, namely 38. The second stunted child is in Cikondang village in 2021. The nutritional status of the third thinnest child There were 32 in Cikondang village in 2021, while the third shortest child was in Cibokor village in 2022 with 14.

The highest number of underweight children was in 2020, namely 142, the second number of underweight children in 2021 was 122. Meanwhile, the lowest number was 26 in 2022. Meanwhile, the highest number of stunted children was in 2020 with 29. The second lowest number was in 2022 with a total of 24. The smallest number will be in 2021 with a total of 9.

If the number of pregnant women with anemia is related to the incidence of stunting at the Cibeber Community Health Center, it can be assumed that in general It is said that there is a relationship between the number of anemic pregnant women and the incidence of stunting at the Cibeber Community Health Center. However, if you analyze the results from table 1 and table 2, based on village origin. So there is a relationship between the number of pregnant women and anemia, which is linked to the incidence of stunting based on village origin, but it is not directly proportional. Because based on the number of pregnant women with anemia, the villages of origin with the most anemia with pregnant women are Mayak Village, Pt Village. Condong and Cibokor Village.

Meanwhile, based on data on the nutritional status of thin children, Cikondang Village, Cihaur Village and Cipetir Village were obtained. Meanwhile, data on the nutritional status of short children is from Cikondang Village and Cibokor

Village. Looking at the data in general, Cikondang Village dominates nutritional status, both in terms of nutritional status in the category of thin children and nutritional status in the category of short children.

CONCLUSION

There is a direct or indirect relationship between pregnant women with anemia, and the incidence of stunting at the Cibeber Community Health Center. This is due to the occurrence of stunting, in line with the results of the program, namely that there are still anemic pregnant women and children with underweight nutritional status and short nutritional status over time. simultaneously

RECOMMENDATION

So that the number of stunting incidents does not appear, it is best that the target of the Maternal and Child Health program can be achieved by carrying out evaluations in several stages. These include evaluation of preparation and implementation.

References

1. Cibeber, BK (2000-2022). *Cibeber Community Health Center PWS KIA Report 2020-2022*. Program Report, Cibeber Community Health Center, Health Service, Cianjur. Retrieved June 30, 2023
2. Dian Anisia Widyaningrum, DA (2018, September). History of Pregnancy Anemia With an incident involving a toddler in Ketandan Dagangan Village, Madiun. *Medika Majapahit, Volume 10. no.2,86-99*. Retrieved April 13, 2024, from <http://ejournal.stikesmajapahit.ac.id/index.php/MM/article/view/291/271>
3. WAHYUNI, NS (2024, April 13). *Ministry of Health, Directorate of General Services Health*. Retrieved July 22, 2022, from Stunting: https://yankes.kemkes.go.id/view_article/462/stunting